
SPEECH COMPRESSION IN SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION: STRATEGIES AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract: The article examines simultaneous translation as one of the most popular linguistic services, discussing its importance in saving time for listeners and speakers. The key strategy of simultaneous translation is described - speech compression, the process of compressing a speaker's speech, which is an integral part of this type of translation. The article emphasizes the relevance of the problem of lack of sufficient training and training of this skill among future interpreters. Various aspects of simultaneous interpreting are studied, including the conditions for speech production, time pressure and mental stress. The issues of probabilistic forecasting, the role of memory and the mechanism of attention distribution in the process of simultaneous translation are also discussed. Important attention is paid to the compression mechanism in simultaneous translation and its impact on the quality and efficiency of translation.

Keywords: simultaneous translation, speech compression, professional translation, simultaneous translation mechanisms, compression mechanism, speech adaptation, oral translation.

Simultaneous translation is becoming one of the most popular linguistic services, as it helps save time for both listeners and the speaker. The process of simultaneous translation has been described not only by linguists, but also by psychologists, neuroscientists and other scientists, but for many it is still a miracle.

One of the key strategies of the type of translation being studied is speech compression, that is, compression of the speaker’s speech, which inevitably occurs in simultaneous translation [1]. This phenomenon is often mentioned in lectures in translation training areas, but often comprehensive research on this issue is not carried out, and in the training process there is no emphasis on training this extremely important skill for an interpreter. Therefore, the problem still remains relevant and requires more detailed study.

Simultaneous translation has always aroused increased interest among foreign and domestic linguists and has been defined by them differently. In particular, as “the combination of a translator’s continuous perception of speech in one language with the reproduction of its meaning in another” [2]; “as a type of activity of an

interpreter, characterized by the pronunciation of the translation text in parallel with the sound of the source text” [3]; as “a professional type of interpreting of conferences, which is carried out simultaneously with the perception of a message in the original language using technical means in a specially equipped booth, and during which - under time pressure - information of a limited volume is processed per unit of text” [4].

Professional simultaneous translation is translation carried out under special conditions. It is characterized by unequal conditions for generating speech in the original language and in the target language, lack of time, as well as increased mental tension, the cause of which is the awareness of the synchronicity of the two languages [5].

Against this background, in the field of simultaneous translation, many questions arose that interested researchers, in particular:

- probabilistic forecasting mechanism;
- the role of memory in the translation process;
- mechanism of attention distribution.

One of the most important issues considered by the theory of simultaneous translation is the compression mechanism in simultaneous translation. Studies have shown that with a carefully worked written translation, the syllabic value of the text increases by one and a half times, and with oral translation, where there is no opportunity for careful development of wording, the text can increase by more than two times [6]. Provided that the speaker delivers a speech at an average or fast pace, then it is difficult, and sometimes impossible, for the translator to have time to pronounce the full text of the translation while the speaker is delivering the speech. Thus, there is a need to consciously reduce the volume of text in the target language. In addition, we must not forget that the speed of speech-mental operations is finite and determined by the natural capabilities and abilities of each individual translator. Therefore, an increase in the rate of speech in the source language leads to an increase in the number of errors during translation.

Speech compression is “... such a compression of speech, determined by the specific conditions of communication, in which only what is necessary for a given communication task is retained, and everything else is discarded” [7].

In fact, speech compression is generated by the specific conditions of the simultaneous interpreter’s activity (time restrictions and the simultaneity of the processes of listening to the speaker’s speech and generating speech in the target language), and its dimensions are determined by the need to maintain an even tempo of the interpreter’s speech in the target language. Speech compression, therefore, is a form of adaptation of translation actions to the conditions of activity [8].

In particular, experts identified the extent of compression by comparing compressed texts obtained as a result of simultaneous translation with uncompressed texts written in writing. As a result, it turned out that compression during translation can reach 30-37%. The main factor influencing the size of the compression of the original message is the speed of speech of the speaker [9].

Compression is typically used when:

- the rate of speech of the speaker is quite high;
- the original message contains repetitions;
- the original message contains insignificant words;
- the speaker's idea can be expressed using fewer words.

It has been proven that in written genres and Internet communication this phenomenon, in addition to the lexical, syntactic and semantic levels, is also observed at the phonological level of language. Compression is also possible at the polysemiotic and graphic level.

In oral genres, compression will be carried out at fewer levels due to the unavailability of graphic means of expression and multimedia information.

In simultaneous translation, many researchers move away from analysing the levels of language, starting to describe compression using a variety of techniques, and present heterogeneous lists that are replete with repetitions and redundancy. For example, researchers consider techniques of a morphological, lexical, syntactic, pragmatic nature, as well as simple omissions [10].

At the lexical level in simultaneous translation, compression is carried out by expressing thoughts in fewer words. Some researchers additionally highlight the syllable level, that is, the conscious choice of a shorter word [11]. But if in the above cases there is a deliberate choice of strategy, then in the case of syllabic compression it is impossible to determine whether the translator used a particular word because it was shorter than the analogue proposed by the researcher, or because it was the only word that at the time of translation came to his mind.

It is also worth noting that the above tactics of syntactic, semantic, lexical compression can be trained and over time begin to be used not only consciously, but also unconsciously, having developed a certain translation style. In the case of syllabic compression, training is possible only by increasing the active vocabulary of words and studying synonymous series. But in the end, it turns out that even knowing these synonyms, a person, due to cognitive characteristics, will have to spend seconds analysing and choosing a shorter word. The translator cannot waste precious time. Therefore, formally this can be considered a way of performing compression, but we do not address it in the framework of our research.

Often, “combined” compression is used, that is, changes at several levels of the language at once. This trend can be seen in many of the examples described in this

article. This suggests that speech compression is a way to solve semantic problems in translation, and structural changes are its consequence.

The translator should understand that compression techniques must be applied depending on the function of the segment in the semantic structure of the statement and on the novelty and value of the information contained in it. For example, it is recommended to resort to compression in the subject line of the message in order to be prepared to listen and pronounce the precision information, terms, main semantic segment. This will greatly facilitate the translator’s task and will reduce the gap between the speaker and avoid a cluttered translation. It is this skill that should be given attention when teaching students simultaneous interpretation.

Thus, it turns out that compression is one of the ways to solve not so much structural as semantic, that is, communicative and functional, tasks during translation [12]. And the translator is a communication specialist. In the process of work, he skilfully chooses tactics to reduce secondary information and preserve the core, the meaning of the statement. At the same time, the translator always evaluates in which case the compression strategy is acceptable and effective, and in which it is unacceptable or undesirable.

Speaking about speech compression techniques in simultaneous translation, it should be noted that it is carried out by replacing words, phrases and sentences that are synonymous or close to them with shorter words, phrases and sentences, omitting segments that duplicate information contained in the previous context, omitting semantic units, redundant in a specific communication situation, and the omission of semantic units that are redundant from the point of view of the communication task, as well as generalization, that is, collapsing the syntagm into a word with a general meaning [13].

In addition, speech compression is accompanied by semantic transformations: compression of the lexical-semantic structure of sentences occurs through reduction and omission of semantic components; the semantic-syntactic organization of sentences is simplified and the figurative nature of syntactic connections is usually enhanced [14].

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